

Cross-lingual Dependency Transfer with Harmonized Indian Language Treebanks

Loganathan Ramasamy and Zdeněk Žabokrtský

Faculty of Mathematics and Physics
Institute of Formal and Applied Linguistics
Charles University in Prague
E-mail: {ramasamy, zabokrtsky}@ufal.mff.cuni.cz

Abstract

One of the most important aspect of cross-lingual dependency transfer is how different annotation styles which often negatively influence the transfer accuracy are handled. The emerging trend is that the annotation style of different language treebanks can be harmonized into one style and the cumbersome manual transformation rules thus can be avoided. In this paper, we use harmonized treebanks (POS tagsets and dependency structures of original treebanks mapped to a common style) for inducing dependencies in a cross-lingual setting. We transfer dependencies using delexicalized parsers that use harmonized version of the original treebanks. We apply this approach to five Indian languages (Hindi, Urdu, Telugu, Bengali and Tamil) and show that best performance can be obtained in delexicalized parsing when the transfer takes place from Indian language (IL) to IL treebanks.

1 Introduction

Many languages including some of the popular languages according to the number of native language speakers do not have treebanks. The reasons for the absence of treebanks for languages that have sizeable population are mainly extraneous such as lack of natural language processing (NLP) research in those languages, research funding, etc. The availability of treebanks for these languages will have tremendous practical value given the fact that treebanks are useful in many practical applications such as machine translation (MT), relation extraction, and so on.

In the case of treebanking, research in recent years focuses on developing methodologies that could reduce years of manual annotation effort by automatically inducing parsers/treebanks for resource-poor languages with varying levels of success. Those methodologies can be broadly categorized

into: (i) unsupervised methods which can parse any language data without any annotated treebank for training, (ii) semi-supervised methods which make use of small amount of treebank annotation to bootstrap the annotation further, and (iii) cross-lingual syntactic annotation transfer through projection (or simply syntactic projection) of annotation from resource-rich source languages to resource-poor target languages. Depending on the resource availability, all three frameworks mentioned above can be combined in a hybrid fashion to obtain better parsing results albeit supervised parsing is most likely to give superior performance.

In this paper, we mainly focus on cross-lingual transfer-based techniques. Recent works on cross-lingual transfer-based techniques [8], [12] and [2] directly transfer the syntax from source language parsers via *delexicalization*, ideally without using any target language resources. *Delexicalized parsing* [15] is a method of using source language parser directly to parse target language sentences. This method requires only part of speech (POS) sequences of source side training data to train delexicalized parsers. It has been shown in [8] that training a parser with POS tags alone achieves parser accuracy comparable (UAS score of 82.5% for a delexicalized parser vs. UAS score of 89.3% for a parser trained with all features for English) to that of supervised parsers. Extending that to parser transfer, delexicalized transfer parsers [8] can give surprisingly better performance than state-of-the-art unsupervised parsers given that source and target languages use the same POS tagset.

It has been shown in earlier works such as [9, 7] that mapping the annotation to common annotation style helps various tasks including POS tagging, grammar induction and cross-lingual dependency transfer. [15] showed that harmonizing POS helps to induce parsers for closely related languages. To the best of our knowledge, this approach has not been explored for Indian languages (IL) which mostly border on under-resourced category except perhaps Hindi. In this paper, we use harmonized treebanks (POS tagsets and dependency structures of original treebanks mapped to a common style) for inducing dependencies for ILs in a cross-lingual setting. We transfer dependencies using delexicalized parsers that use harmonized version of the original treebanks. We use both non-IL and IL source treebank parsers to parse target ILs. In the results section, we particularly show that parsers trained on ILs can help other ILs.

Section 2 discusses the delexicalized parsing and the harmonization of IL treebanks to a common annotation style with respect to POS and dependencies. Section 3 presents the data and experimental settings. Section 4 presents delexicalized parsing results for ILs.

2 Delexicalized Parsing

In projection based approaches [4], the projected structures (as a result of projection alone or resulting from parsers trained on projected treebanks) for the target language sentences will have some systematic differences with respect to the target treebank annotation style since the projected structures follow source treebank annotation style. One must implement some transformation rules similar to [4] to overcome the drop in evaluation accuracy due to annotation differences. Other alternative is to map both source and target annotation styles to adhere to a common standard [14, 7].

Delexicalized parsing is the method of parsing target language sentences using a parser trained on a source language treebank. The parser trained on the source treebank does not use source wordforms (hence the name delexicalized), but relies mainly on POS tags and other non-lexical features associated with the source trees. Such a parser can be used to parse target language sentences provided target language sentences too are tagged with the same POS tagset as that of the one used in the source treebank. To address the annotation differences at dependency level, we adopt the strategy of using harmonized treebanks i.e., treebanks mapped to a common annotation style. The following subsections describe the IL treebank data and provide relevant information regarding the harmonization of IL treebanks under HamleDT [14], a large scale treebank harmonization project.

2.1 POS harmonization

One of the main requirements in delexicalized parsing is a common POS tagset. Common POS tagset is essential for both source side parser training and target side parsing. At present, there are two sets of treebanks that have common annotation scheme and are easily accessible: (i) treebanks mapped to the Prague Dependency Treebank (PDT) style annotation [14] via harmonization (also known as HamleDT treebanks) and (ii) treebanks based on universal dependency annotation [7]. HamleDT [14] harmonizes treebanks by mapping POS, dependency relations and dependency structure to PDT style annotation.

Lang.	Source	# Sentences		Tagset size		
		train	test	dep.	CPOSTAG	POSTAG
Bengali (bn)	ICON2010 [3]	979	150	42	14	21
Hindi (hi)	COLING2012 [3]	12041	1233	119	36	20
Tamil (ta)	TamilTB 1.0 [10]	480	120	25	12	465
Telugu (te)	ICON2010 [3]	1300	150	41	16	24
Urdu (ur)	UDT [1]	2808	313	71	15	29

Table 1: IL treebank statistics

HamleDT at present contains 30 existing treebanks harmonized into PDT style annotation as well as Stanford dependencies [11]. 4 out of 5 IL treebanks¹ shown in Table 1 except Urdu (**ur**)² treebank are already POS and dependency harmonized in HamleDT. Thus, we make use of the harmonized IL treebanks in HamleDT for our delexicalized parser experiments. POS harmonization in HamleDT is done as follows: the POS tagset of original treebanks are mapped to Intersect features [13]. Intersect features are detailed morphological features that any POS tag(set) can be mapped into, i.e., any tag is a list of morphological features (Intersect). This conversion is done via tagset drivers. Tagset drivers are written for each treebank tagset in HamleDT. Captured Intersect features for each wordform are then converted into positional tags - the style PDT uses for POS annotation.

Treebank	Orig. size	PDT fine	PDT coarse
Bengali (bn)	21	29	12
Hindi (hi)	36	344	12
Tamil (ta)	465	79	10
Telugu (te)	23	58	12
Urdu (ur)	29	10	10

Table 2: POS tagset size: original vs. harmonized

For all the IL treebanks, harmonized fine-grained PDT style positional tags obtained from Intersect features are larger than the original POS tagset size. Since each fine-grained positional tag is a detailed morphological tag and each position represents a particular morphological phenomenon, it is easy to extract coarse-grained tags to tailor to the needs of various NLP tasks. We use the 1st position of fine-grained positional tag as coarse-grained tag.

Table 2 shows the POS tagset size of original and harmonized IL treebanks (measured only using the training section of the treebanks in Table 1). POS tagset size of the original treebanks - {**bn**, **hi**, **te**, **ur**} are relatively lower than the Tamil (**ta**) treebank. *AnnCorra* is a POS/chunk tagset standard³ for Indian languages. *AnnCorra* POS tagset is similar to PennTagset [5] in terms of tags (most of them are reused) and its com-

¹Throughout the paper we refer IL treebanks using language names/codes (ISO) instead of their actual treebank names. For example, when we say ‘Tamil (**ta**)’ or ‘**ta**’ treebank, it refers to the actual treebank described in the 2nd column of Table 1.

²We harmonized the original Urdu (**ur**) treebank POS tagset to Intersect features. We mapped only major POS information to Intersect features, at the moment, the POS harmonization does not make use of features supplied by the Urdu (**ur**) treebank. Coarse/fine-grained PDT style tags can be obtained from Intersect features.

³*AnnCorra*: POS tagging guidelines for Indian languages - <http://ltrc.iiit.ac.in/tr031/posguidelines.pdf>

pactness. Treebanks `{bn, hi, te, ur}` use AnnCorra scheme whereas Tamil (`ta`) uses PDT style positional tags for the treebank POS annotation. In addition to POS tags, AnnCorra also includes chunk level tags in the annotation. These tags (such as noun chunk, verb chunk, etc.) are included in treebanks `{bn, te}` as coarse-grained tags (CPOSTAG column in the CoNLL data) and in `hi` as one of the features (through `chunkId`, `chunkType` in FEATS column) in the CoNLL data. Table 2 also shows the tagset size of treebanks after harmonization (columns 3 and 4).

Harmonized fine-grained tagset size of the Hindi (`hi`) treebank is larger than `{bn, te}` treebanks. This could be attributed to a more detailed inclusion of morphological features in the Hindi (`hi`) treebank annotation in comparison to `{bn, te}`. Moreover, the Hindi (`hi`) treebank has been evolving and the treebank comes from 2012 shared task whereas both `{bn, te}` come from 2010 ICON shared task. For all harmonized treebanks, coarse-grained tagset size is similar to universal POS tagset [9]. Our coarse-grained tag inventory contains 12 tags in total: adjective (A), numeral (C), adverb (D), interjection (I), conjunction (J), noun (N), pronoun (P), verb (V), preposition (R), particle (T), unknown (X), and punctuation (Z).

2.2 Dependency harmonization

This section describes dependency harmonization of IL treebanks in HamleDT. Dependency harmonization is important for the reason that it can minimize errors that occur due to annotation differences at structural level during delexicalized transfer. For example, if one were to parse Hindi sentences using the delexicalized source parser trained on a Czech (`cs`) treebank, the parser would always make postpositions the head of postpositional phrases. But the Hindi (`hi`) treebank makes the noun argument the head of postpositional phrases. So, the evaluation would often underestimate this type of stylistic variations due to annotation differences. This type of errors can be avoided if treebanks follow same convention regarding annotations. Dependency harmonization in HamleDT is done includes mapping dependency relations to PDT analytical functions and transforming

The delexicalized transfer approach requires both source and target IL treebanks to be harmonized at both POS and structural level. IL treebanks (Table 1) except Urdu (`ur`) have already been harmonized in addition to dozens of other treebanks in HamleDT.

Table 3 compares original IL treebanks and harmonized IL treebanks. Evaluation with and without punctuation are shown under columns 3 and 2 respectively. The table shows that Hindi (`hi`) treebank is the most affected by harmonization at structural level.

Tamil (`ta`) treebank did not require too much harmonization since the treebank already follows Prague dependency style annotation for most of the syntactic phenomena. Harmonized Bengali (`bn`) and Telugu (`te`) treebanks

too didn't change from their original structures. At the moment, Urdu (**ur**) treebank has not been harmonized at the dependency level.

Lang.	No punc	With punc
Bengali (bn)	99.9	99.1
Hindi (hi)	58.0	56.3
Tamil (ta)	100.0	99.8
Telugu (te)	100.0	99.4
Urdu (ur)	-	-

Table 3: UAS scores between original and harmonized treebanks

3 Experiments

The main goal of this experiment is to parse ILs using other language parsers (delexicalized).

We consider left and right-branching trees as one of our baseline. We also provide supervised parser results for comparison, this could in fact indicate the upper limit that other cross-lingual approaches can aim for. Indian languages are head-final in many respects and have a tendency to be left-branching. So, one can expect the left-branching accuracy to be higher than the right-branching accuracy. As a second baseline, we train supervised parsers on the training section of the treebanks in Table 1. We train our models with MSTParser [6] (version-0.5.0). We train all our parsing models with 2nd order, non-projective settings. We provide supervised parser results for both POS harmonized and POS+dependency harmonized version of the IL treebanks.

We perform delexicalized transfer experiment in two settings: (i) with POS harmonization and (ii) with POS and dependency harmonization.

In *POS harmonization* experiment, we use the source structure as it is from the native treebank annotation style, but we use coarse-grained harmonized POS tags i.e., only the 1st position of the fine-grained tags. We then train a regular parser on the POS harmonized data, however, without source forms. For testing, we first tag the target test data and parse the target sentences with the trained model - again by removing target word-forms before the parsing step. It must also be noted that the target tagset should match the harmonized POS tagset; in our case - PDT tagset. Target tagging step can be done in a number of ways,

1. train harmonized POS tagger and tag target sentences directly with the harmonized POS tagger.
2. train a POS tagger with the native POS tagset, and perform harmonization after tagging the target sentences with the native POS tagger.

3. obtain harmonized POS tags for target sentences in an unsupervised manner, for example, by projecting the source tags onto the target—similar to [8].

The first two methods require annotated data (from target language) for training the POS tagger. The third method requires only annotated data in source language. We do target tagging according to (2).

For this experiment, we show results for parsing five ILs (target) using delexicalized parsers trained on 30 treebanks in HamleDT (source). We use POS harmonized treebanks to train delexicalized parsers. POS harmonized treebanks are obtained from HamleDT 2.0 [14] which is both POS and dependency harmonized to PDT style annotation. This experiment requires only harmonization of POS tags of the original treebanks. So we replace original POS tags with harmonized POS tags in the original treebanks. We use coarse-grained harmonized POS tag instead of full length PDT style tag.

Four (**bn**, **hi**, **ta**, **te**) out of five treebanks mentioned in Table 1 are harmonized in the HamleDT. However, for **ta** as source, we harmonize the current version of the Tamil dependency treebank (TamilTB 1.0) and train delexicalized parser on it. HamleDT 2.0 contains harmonized version of TamilTB.v0.1. This makes sense because Tamil (**ta**) treebank mentioned in Table 1 uses TamilTB 1.0 data. Urdu (**ur**) is not part of HamleDT yet, however, we do POS harmonization separately because Urdu (**ur**) test data needs to be POS harmonized before parsing.

In *POS+dependency harmonization* experiment, we train delexicalized parsers that are both POS and dependency harmonized. This experiment is similar to the POS only harmonization experiment, but it uses fully harmonized HamleDT 2.0 treebanks. We train delexicalized parsers on HamleDT 2.0 treebanks, again by replacing forms by coarse-grained harmonized POS tags. We harmonize target test data (POS and dependency structure) before parsing with delexicalized parsers. We do not have dependency harmonization for Urdu (**ur**). So, the results section do not include Urdu (**ur**).

4 Results

We provide baseline/supervised parsing results (Table 4) and delexicalized parsing results (Table 5, with ILs as source) for five ILs. All the results in this section show unlabeled attachment scores (UAS). We also trained delexicalized parsers from non-IL treebanks (Table 6) from HamleDT, but their scores were much lower than IL treebanks as source.

The average accuracy in **bold** for ILs in Table 5 indicate that the numbers are higher than the left/right baseline in Table 4. Within ILs, **hi**, **ta** seem to act as best source for each other, and similarly **bn**, **te** too act as best source for each other. Urdu (**ur**) benefits from **bn**, **te**.

Lang.	POS harmonized				POS+dep harmonized			
	left	right	pred.	gold	left	right	pred.	gold
bn	53.6	04.6	72.1	77.7	53.6	04.6	73.0	77.8
hi	24.4	27.3	76.0	78.5	53.3	07.7	75.8	78.4
ta	50.9	09.5	57.6	67.2	50.9	09.5	58.7	68.6
te	65.8	02.4	82.6	86.2	65.8	02.4	83.1	86.2
ur	42.9	06.3	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 4: Left/right baseline and supervised parser results: POS harmonized vs. POS+dep harmonized. *pred.* - POS tags are obtained from a supervised tagger; *gold* - gold tags.

Source	bn		hi		ta		te		ur	
	D_P	D_{PD}	D_P	D_{PD}	D_P	D_{PD}	D_P	D_{PD}	D_P	D_{PD}
bn	-	-	27.8	33.1	34.8	36.1	78.6	78.2	58.6	-
hi	57.7	55.1	-	-	41.6	46.4	67.6	68.3	48.7	-
ta	57.3	55.9	34.2	61.7	-	-	69.1	69.6	42.6	-
te	63.9	62.4	21.9	24.1	22.5	26.1	-	-	53.9	-
avg	59.6	57.8	28.0	39.6	33	36.2	71.8	72.0	51.0	-

Table 5: Delexicalized parser results in the case of ILs as source. D_P - POS harmonization; D_{PD} - POS+dependency harmonization;

When we compare delexicalized transfer of all HamleDT treebanks to ILs and IL-IL delexicalized transfer i.e., **bn-hi**, **bn-ta**, **bn-te**, **bn-ur**, **hi-bn** and so on in Table 6 and 5, there’s a discernible improvement in average transfer accuracy for IL-IL transfer. There’s a big gain in the average accuracy (44.1% to 59.6% for **bn**, 26.5% to 33.0% for **ta** and so on) for all ILs except Hindi (**hi**) treebank for which the average accuracy drops from 30.2% to 28.0%. Hindi (**hi**) treebank does not seem to benefit from closely related source language treebanks, in fact, language isolate **eu** as source gives the best result (49.2%). In Table 5, parsers trained from **{eu, hu, la, tr}** are overall best source to parse ILs (each source crosses the left baseline for at least 3 target ILs). **{ro, de}** source parsers did not cross the left baseline for any of the target ILs. Most of the source languages (mostly Indo-European) did not cross the left baseline for most ILs.

In terms of language relatedness - Hindi, Urdu and Bengali belong to *Indo-Aryan* family, and Tamil and Telugu belong to *Dravidian* family. But the results are quite contradictory at least in identifying which language treebank is the best source for parsing the test data. Though the original treebanks of **{hi, bn, te, ur }** follow similar annotation styles, at the data level, the treebanks are quite different. For example, the average training sentence lengths of treebanks **{bn, te}** are 6.6 and 3.9 words, respectively.

Source	Family	bn		hi		ta		te		ur	
		D_P	D_{PD}								
ar	Semitic	23.1	22.4	26.5	14.4	11.7	11.9	35.4	35.9	23.4	-
bg	IE	32.1	39.5	36.9	18.1	17.7	19	50.4	59.4	21.2	-
bn	IE	-	-	27.8	33.1	34.8	36.1	78.6	78.2	58.6	-
ca	IE	49.3	53.7	26.4	14.5	14.2	15	70.3	73.9	35.1	-
cs	IE	38.1	39.3	32.9	20.2	18	18.1	53.1	53.5	27.6	-
da	IE	35	40.8	30.1	28.4	23.2	33.9	40.6	45.9	35.8	-
de	IE	41.2	45.6	22.1	27.3	30.2	31.9	56.3	58.3	32.4	-
el	IE	39.8	41.4	28.5	17.2	27.3	27.1	57.2	58.2	33.5	-
en	IE	40.9	44.7	44.4	22.8	35.5	29.5	55.1	57.2	32.4	-
es	IE	48.7	50.7	26.6	15.3	15.5	16.4	65.4	74.7	35.2	-
et	Uralic	51.1	52	27	47.6	37.2	36.3	66.4	63.6	43	-
eu	L. Isolate	54.4	56.4	49.2	39.3	47.4	47.8	66.3	67.5	48.2	-
fa	IE	43.7	43.6	27.8	23.4	15.1	16.2	63.7	65.4	28.6	-
fi	Uralic	49.6	53.6	38.8	46.8	38.6	42	59.9	65.8	37.9	-
grc	IE	54.4	55.9	21.9	29	32.5	32.3	64.1	71.5	41.3	-
hi	IE	57.7	55.1	-	-	41.6	46.4	67.6	68.3	48.7	-
hu	Uralic	53.2	58.9	26.8	50	34.7	38.1	65.9	66.3	47	-
it	IE	39.8	44.7	25.8	11.7	16.1	16.4	57.2	59.9	24.6	-
ja	Japonic	53.6	55	24.1	50.7	43.5	44.2	68.3	70.7	37.1	-
la	IE	55.4	54.6	24.7	24.7	29.1	28.1	67.5	67.5	51.3	-
nl	IE	33.7	38.9	32.7	22.5	21.3	22.9	48.7	54.3	38.1	-
pt	IE	20.9	23.7	34.2	20.7	17.9	19.5	27.2	29	13.3	-
ro	IE	31.2	31.8	22.7	8.8	7.1	7.4	50.6	50.9	17.4	-
ru	IE	36.9	37.9	31.8	25.9	17.6	18.9	56.7	58.9	29.6	-
sk	IE	35.4	38.4	34.3	21	22.5	22.4	54.5	55.5	25.4	-
sl	IE	39.5	41.4	29.5	15.5	12.9	12.5	60.4	58.5	22.9	-
sv	IE	38.9	43.6	44.4	27.4	37.6	38.4	49.4	52.6	30.2	-
ta	Dravidian	57.3	55.9	34.2	61.7	-	-	69.1	69.6	42.6	-
te	Dravidian	63.9	62.4	21.9	24.1	22.5	26.1	-	-	53.9	-
tr	Altaic	59.6	59.2	22.2	51.1	45.5	46.4	71.7	71.2	45	-
avg		44.1	46.2	30.2	28	26.5	27.6	58.5	60.8	35.4	-

Table 6: Delexicalized parser results with harmonized HamleDT treebanks as source and ILs as target. *Source* - language code of the treebank, the actual treebank sources are described in [14]; D_P - POS harmonization; D_{PD} - POS+dependency harmonization; IE - Indo-European; L. isolate - language isolate;

Whereas the average training sentence length for Hindi (**hi**) treebank is 22.3 words. For **{ta, ur}** treebanks, the average training sentence lengths are 15.1 and 13.1, respectively. That means, the treebanks **{bn, te}** may not have sufficient representation of structures at the syntactic level to be efficient source languages for parsing Hindi sentences. This also partly explains why the treebanks **{hi, ta}** are best source for each other. But this reasoning does not apply well for Urdu (**ur**) because **{bn, te}** act as best sources than **{hi, ta}**.

5 Conclusion

In this paper we tried to induce dependencies for five Indian languages (not so resource-rich) using the cross-lingual approach known as delexicalized parsing. The main difference between the methodology we used in the paper and earlier approaches is in the use of harmonized treebanks. Harmonized treebanks not only facilitate the use of other language tools and resources in a cross-lingual setting (without the need to write transformation rules on a case-by-case basis), but will also help parsing evaluation based on a consistent annotation style. We compared our results mainly with left/right baseline owing to the strong left-branching preference of IL treebanks. The results show that best overall performance can be obtained in delexicalized parsing when the transfer takes place from IL to IL treebanks.

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